

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Work commitment among teachers: The roles of compensation and performance appraisal in Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the potential influence of compensation and performance appraisal on work commitment among teachers in Ikenne, Ogun state. Descriptive research design was adopted and the sample size of one hundred and forty-one (141) teachers from five (5) secondary schools in the area of study were selected through total enumeration technique. Three validated instruments namely Work Commitment scale, Compensation scale and Performance appraisal scale with reliability coefficient of 0.53, 0.898 and 0.788 respectively were adopted and used for data collection. One research question was analyzed using descriptive statistics while four hypotheses postulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using multiple regression analysis. The finding of this study revealed significant combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on teachers work commitment ($F_{(2,138)} = 59.855, P < .05$). It further revealed that compensation and performance appraisal jointly accounted for about 46% of variance in teachers work commitment (Adj. $R^2 = .457$). A significant relative influence of the independent variables on work commitment was also discovered while findings also show that monetary compensation is the package mostly available to teachers. Based on the findings, it was concluded that teachers should be compensated for their hard work as it makes them more committed to their work. It was recommended that that school administrators should administer performance appraisals to ensure teachers are more productive in their work. Compensations such as promotions, monetary rewards and awards should be based on the results of these performance appraisals so as to ensure commitment of the teachers.

Key words: Compensation; Performance appraisal; Teachers; Work commitment

1. Introduction

Every academic institution aims to produce the best set of students, be it within a state or within the entire country and this cannot be achieved if the teachers tasked with impacting knowledge in the students are not committed to their work. The sensitive and important role of teachers in nation building necessitates that they are compensated accordingly. However, the economic state of the country, amongst many other factors, appears to impact negatively on the adequate compensation of school teachers. Ogunnaike and Oyewunmi (2016) states that the subject and practice of teacher compensation is crucial to their work life. The progress of the nation is a reflection of the quality of its people modeled by teachers for being the source of inspiration and guidance in their academic life (Ballantine & Spade, 2009). Commitment is agreed to be a vital factor in organizations because it was found to enhance organizational citizenship behavior, teacher performance, and more involvement in work. Commitment refers to an individual's attraction and attachment to the work and the organization. The changing nature of the work environment has necessitated different management approaches. However, an important and stable factor has been the ways in which managers and employers motivate their workers to help achieve not only the organizational goals but also their own personal ones (Eshun and Duah, 2011). Raza & Ahmed (2017) identified three types of work commitment as affective, continuance, and normative.

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Affective work commitment refers to the teachers' willingness to stay within an organization because of the belief that their role and job goals are clearly defined and receive management support. While continuance work commitment refers to the benefits of remaining within the organization because of the fewer work opportunities that exist outside the organization and the perceived costs of leaving current organization will be higher. Whereas, normative work commitment refers to a teacher's willingness to remain with the organization because of his or her feeling of obligation. In this context, a teacher thinks that he or she ought to remain with a particular organization because he or she believes it is morally right to do so. Additionally, Ogunnaike & Oyewunmi (2016) classified four forms of commitment. First is the "want to" commitment. In this scenario, teachers are dedicated to their employing organization and are willing to exceed expectations in tasks. The second form is the "have to" commitment. This refers to a situation where teachers feel trapped. The "ought to" commitment implies that teachers feel obligated to remain with an organization. The fourth category is the detached or uncommitted group of teachers. This type of teachers are not interested in remaining with the organization and are consistently searching for new career opportunities. According to Bragg (2002), 20-30% of the modern-day workforce is in this situation.

Furthermore, teacher commitment can be focused on various targets which are considered to be of importance to the teacher (Cohen 2003). The foci include commitment to the academic institution, occupation, team, customer, supervisor or trade unions. The foci are influenced by values, morals, performance, compliance, competency and continuance culture of the organization also referred to as dimensions of commitment. Latore, Guest, Rams and Gracia (2016) posits that the different forms and dimensions of commitment are critical in development of HR strategies, policies and practices aimed at increasing commitment at workplace. The philosophy of compensation policy is largely guided by values of transparency, compliance and performance (Zacher, Chan & Baker, 2015).

The level of commitment teachers put into their work can be affected by how well they are compensated. Compensation refers to both monetary and non-monetary benefits provided to teachers in return for rendering mental and physical services to the organization (Ogunnaike & Oyewunmi, 2016). The sensitive and important role of teachers in nation building necessitates that they are compensated accordingly. However, the economic state of the country, amongst many other factors, appears to impact negatively on the adequate compensation for teachers. Compensation has long been considered as one of the most important rewards for work (Adler and Ghiselli, 2015; Raza & Ahmed, 2017).

The implementation of effective compensation policies can be difficult and the negative consequences of poor implementation can override any positive benefits of compensation policies (Leob 2009; Akinlolu & Maina, 2020). Furthermore, compensation may achieve several purposes like assisting in recruitment, job performance, and work commitment because compensation is the glue that binds the teachers and the academic institution together in an organized sector, which is further codified in the form of a contract or a mutually binding legal document that spells out exactly how much should be paid to the teacher and the components of the compensation package (Cascio, 2013).

Another important variable that could affect teachers' commitment to work is performance appraisal. Many performance appraisal systems are weighted heavily toward accountability rather than the growth and development of teachers and their teaching practices. Many performance appraisal systems have failed to inform teachers about what needs to be improved in relation to their development. Within the performance appraisal process, standards provide scope for teachers and school leaders to make informed decisions about teaching performance and may assist in identifying future areas for growth and development (Bartlett, 2000). Apart from the aforementioned points above, there are many factors that influence the teachers' job commitment such as aptitude, attitude, subject mastery, teaching methodology, personal characteristics, the classroom environment, general mental ability, personality, relations with students, preparation and planning, effectiveness in presenting subject matters, relations with other staff, self-improvement, relations with parents and community, poise, intellect, teaching techniques, interactions with students, teaching competence demonstrated, motivational skills, fairness in grading and teachers' attitude toward the students (Raza & Ahmed, 2017).

Consequently, it should be noted that the success, survival and competing power of organizations depends on the commitment of their members, and this may to a large extent depend on how satisfied the teachers are in respect of the schools' appraisal mechanism and compensation plans. It is in line with the above that this study seeks to study the roles of compensation and performance appraisal to teachers' work commitment in Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to evaluate compensation and performance appraisal as determinants of work commitment among teachers in Ikenne, Ogun State. Thus, specifically this study seeks to:

Identify the type of compensation packages available to teachers in Ikenne.

Determine whether compensation and performance appraisal will have any significant combined influence on work commitment among teachers.

Evaluate if compensation will have any relative influence on work commitment among teachers.

Determine if there will be any significant relative influence of performance appraisal on work commitment among teachers.

1.1. Research Questions

What are the types of compensation packages available to teachers in Ikenne?

1.2. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested during the study:

- There is no significant combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on teachers' work commitment.
- There is no significant relative influence of compensation on teachers' work commitment.
- There is no significant relative influence of performance appraisal on teachers' work commitment.

2. Literature review

2.1. The Concept of Compensation

Compensation can be defined as the sum total of all the rewards that the employers provide to employees for the labor rendered to them. Compensation according to Walker (1998) is what an employee is given as a salary, bonus and other benefits such as monetary interchanges that employees get as a result of improved performance. Cole, (1997) further defines compensation as a direct monetary payout that include salaries, bonuses, commissions and wages paid to employees. Financial compensation by character includes indirect monetary compensation like the pension schemes that are not part of direct financial compensation. In addition, non-monetary rewards are inclusive of the job itself and the overall job environment. The provision of equal and fair compensation are the main challenges that companies encounter on issues to do with pay and salary issues and the services rendered by the employee should be paid for reasonably.

Akpan (2013) made it clear that compensation is motivation for a worker. He alleged that in Nigeria, teachers are not given adequate priority as stipulated in the revised National Policy on Education of 2013. He went further to report that teachers in Nigeria bitterly complain of lack of motivational incentives for them, such as housing, transport, medical allowances, merit awards, in-service training, leave allowances and bonuses. The outcome of this is that when teachers are poorly remunerated, their motivation will be low, and this will spill over to students' achievement in various subjects due to the lack of passion or zeal with which teachers dish out curricula content to them.

2.2. The Concept of work commitment

Work commitment is an attachment an employee has to their organization which affects his level of satisfaction and engagement. It is crucial to assess employee commitment since it is a key element in organizational success. Building work commitment is one of the main parts of the organizational growth and development (Dinc, 2017). The performance of employees will increase from commitment employees. Furthermore, individuals who have work commitment will show three attitudes which embrace identification with the organization's goals and values, involvement and striving for the organizational growth and progress, and loyalty to stay as a member or part of the organization (Uwannah, 2017). Teachers' work commitment is an essential aspect in achieving school's success because highly committed teachers will devote more of their time and put extra effort in their work to attain school's goals (Onaolapo, Olajiga & Onaolapo, 2019). When teachers are committed, school will be more effective and productive. A long-term success of a school depends on the commitment of the teachers. Improving the level of work commitment of an individual can reduce the turnover intention in an organization. Furthermore, Othman and Kasuma (2017) opined that work commitment is an essential part of an organization's excellence.

2.3. The Concept of Performance Appraisal

Performance appraisal system refers to all those procedures that are applied to evaluate the personality, the performance, and the potential of a deployed individual and communicating the results of the evaluation to him for the purpose of rewarding or developing him. Alo (1999) defines performance appraisal as a process involving deliberate stock taking of the success, which an individual or organization has achieved in performing assigned tasks or meeting set goals over a period of time. It therefore shows that performance appraisal practices should be deliberate and not by accident. It calls for serious approach to knowing how the individual is doing in performing his or her tasks.

Alshaikhi and Alshaiki (2021) submits that performance appraisal is a system which provides schools with a means of identifying not only what people's performance levels are but which areas those levels need to be improved if maximum use is to be made of human resource. According to Atiomo (2000), every academic institution should ensure that the individual is clearly aware of what his functions and responsibilities are to make performance appraisal effective. Kagema and Irungu (2018) opines that performance appraisal is the process through which schools take stock of its manpower in terms of its present performance, the aptitude and interest of each person, his strengths and weaknesses and his potential for growth. The data emerging from such an exercise constitutes the primary database for individual development and should be communicated to the subordinate.

Similarly, Iorfa (2014) avers that effective performance appraisal systems usually are made up of two basic systems operating in conjunction: an evaluation system and a feedback system. The main aim of the evaluation system is to identify the performance gap. This gap is the shortfall that occurs when performance does not meet the standard set by the academic institution as acceptable. The main aim of the feedback system is to inform the teacher about the quality of his or her performance. However, the flow of information should not be one way. The appraisers also should receive feedback from the teacher about job problems, difficulties, challenges and so on. The feedback system is therefore set to enhance the flow of post-appraisal information between appraiser and appraisee.

In addition, performance appraisals can help schools in several ways. First, they can enhance the quality of organizational decisions ranging from pay raises to promotions to discharges. Second, performance appraisals can enhance the quality of individual decisions, ranging from career choices to the development of future strengths. Third, performance appraisals can affect teachers' views of and attachment to their academic institution. Finally, formal performance appraisals provide a rational, legally defensible basis for personnel decisions. Some schools tend to overlook performance appraisal and believe in the philosophy that if you trust your teachers, they would do well for fear of breaking your trust but unfortunately Abdu and Nzilano (2018) discovered in his studies that it is not always so. Furthermore, employees' perception of fairness in their institutions performance appraisal experience can increase their faith in the system, thereby, resulting in an increased commitment to their organizations or jobs. According to Kyeremeh and Pimpong (2018), employees who perceived recognition of their performance to the organization in their performance appraisal system, have a higher tendency to be committed to their jobs. However, with a perceived absence of a high-quality performance appraisal experience, employees are unlikely to become committed and consequently feel no sense of reciprocal obligation (Wapmuk, Botsha, Yakubu, Nanfa & Goma, 2022).

2.4. Compensation, Performance Appraisal and Job Commitment

Muazza, Noviyanti, Makmur and Hidayat (2019) carried out a research on working compensation and climate on teachers' performance in which it was concluded that there was no relationship between working compensation and teacher performance but in the works of Akafo and Boateng (2015) on compensation determinants and its impact on employees in private tertiary institutions in Ghana, it was found that compensation in private tertiary institutions in Ghana was determined by both internal and external factors with the former being more dominant and compensation fixed on the bases of tenure and job position positively influenced the maintenance of organizational membership and financial rewards only increased continuance commitment but not affective commitment.

Likewise, Subekti and Setyadi (2016) on their research discovered that performance appraisal system is stronger in influencing employee commitment to work than compensation. Sari, Noviyanti, Hendra, Harja & Hidayat (2019) studies concluded that adequate compensation enhances work commitment. When teachers are adequately compensated, performance will be enhanced and intention to leave the organization will be drastically reduced. This study found that compensation has a significant relationship with work commitment. It is therefore recommended that appropriate and timely compensation be deployed to facilitate increased work commitment. The subject of compensation poses a critical challenge for the Nigerian workforce. Particularly within the public sector, employees have to constantly resort to industrial actions to receive commensurate compensation for their effort (Yusuf, Afolabi & Oyetayo, 2014). There is a critical need for all relevant stakeholders to jointly resolve issues relating to compensation and design strategies, to

ensure appropriate and timely compensation of teaching staff, as well as other support personnel. This will have a positive impact on performance outcomes and enhance the commitment levels of employees.

Kumar (2016) and Werang, Agung and Agung (2017) in their different submissions contende that poor compensation is a major cause of teachers' job dissatisfaction and concluded that the compensation the teachers receive does not match with their job description. The study also concludes that the allowances such as medical allowance, transportation allowance, and retirement allowance that the teachers receive affect their job satisfaction.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research design

The survey research design was used for this study.

3.1.1. Population

Due to the small number of teachers in secondary schools in Ikenne, total enumeration was used to select all the one hundred and forty-one (141) teachers in the selected schools

3.1.2. Instrumentation

Section A of the instrument used for data collection captured information on the participants demographic information. Compensation Scale (CS), a 5-item scale was self-developed on 5-point Likert ranging from 5 = strongly agree to 1 = strongly disagree was used to measure compensation. This instrument has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.898. Performance appraisal was measured with a scale developed by Iqbal, Ahmad, Haider & Batool (2013) with Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of .788. Work commitment scale has 5-items and was developed by Alam (2011) with a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient value of .53 as reported by the developers.

Simple percentages and frequency counts was used to analyse section A which is the demographic section, mean and standard deviation was used to analyse the research question while multiple regression analysis was used to analyse hypothesis 1 – 4 all at 0.05 level of significance.

3.2. Presentation of demographic data

Table 1 Frequency Distribution for Demographic Data

Variable	Category	Number of Teachers	Percentage
Gender	Male	66	46.8
	Female	75	53.2
Age (in years)	20-25	9	6.4
	26-31	19	13.5
	32-38	42	29.8
	39-45	39	27.7
	46 & above	32	22.7
Religion	Christianity	75	53.2
	Islam	56	39.7
	Others	10	7.1

School	Babcock university High school	20	14.2
	Ilisan High School		
	Remo Methodist High School	22	15.6
	Ikenne Community High school	26	18.4
	Ositelu Memorial College		
	Isanbi Comprehensive High school	30	21.3
		23	16.3
		20	14.2
Sector of School	Public	98	69.5
	Private	43	30.5
Years of Experience	1-5	16	11.3
	6-10	37	26.2
	11-15	38	27.0
	16-20	32	22.7
	21 & above	18	12.8
Teachers Receipt of Compensation	Yes	141	100.0
	No	0	0.0

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Results in Table 4.1.1 revealed that a majority of the participants (53%) were female while (47%) of the participants were male. Thus, there were more female than male teachers in this study. The greatest proportion of the participants (30%) were 32-38 years old. This was successively followed by those who were 39-45 years old (28%), 46years and above (23%), 26-31years old (14%) and 20-25years old (6%).

A majority of the participants (53%) were Christians. This was successively followed by Muslims (40%) and adherent of other religions (7%). The greatest proportion of the participants (21%) were from Ikenne community high school. This was successively followed by those who were from Remo Methodist high school (18%), Ositelu Memorial College (16%), Ilisan High School (16%), Babcock University High School (14%) and Isanbi Comprehensive High School (14%).

A majority of participants (69%) worked in public schools, while 31% of the participants worked in private schools. The greatest proportion of the participants (27%) had 11-15years of experience. This was successively followed by those who had 6-10years (26%), 16-20years (23%), 21years and above (13%) and 1-5years of experience (11%). Finally, virtually all the participants (100%) were of the view that teachers receive compensation for their work.

3.3. Research Question 1: What are the types of compensation packages available to teachers in Ikenne LGA

Table 2 Compensation packages available to teachers

	Number of Teachers	Percentage
Monetary	73	53.9
Promotion	23	16.3
Recognition/Award	25	17.7
Others	17	12.1

Results in Table 4.1.2 above revealed that a majority of the participants (54%) claimed that monetary compensation package is available for teachers. This was successively followed by those who chose recognition/award (18%), promotion (16%) and other compensation packages (12%).

3.4. Test of Hypotheses

3.4.1. Hypothesis One

H01: There is no significant combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on teachers work commitment

Table 3 Model summary and coefficients of the multiple regression analysis for combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on work commitment

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	932.411	2	466.206	59.855	0.000
Residual	1074.866	138	7.789		
Total	2007.277	140			
Model Summary: R= .682; R2 = .465; Adj.R2 =.457; St. Error = 2.79086					

Dependent Variable: Work Commitment

Predictors: (constant), compensation, performance appraisal

Table 4.2.1 above showed significant results ($F_{(2,138)} = 59.855, P < .05$). The null hypothesis which stated that there will be no significant combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on teachers work commitment is therefore rejected in favor of an alternative hypothesis. It is subsequently concluded that there will be significant combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on teachers work commitment. Table 4.2.1 further revealed that compensation and performance appraisal jointly accounted for about 46% of variance in teachers work commitment ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = .457$)

3.4.2. Hypothesis Two

H02: There is no significant relative influence of compensation on teachers work commitment.

Table 4 Coefficients of the simple linear regression analysis for the influence of compensation on work commitment.

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
1 (constant)	9.067	0.747		7.951	0.000
Compensation	0.461	0.048	0.628	9.516	0.000

Dependent Variable: Work Commitment

Results in Table 4.2.2 were significant ($\text{Beta} = .628, t = 9.516, P < .05$). The null hypothesis which stated that there will be no significant relative influence of compensation on teachers work commitment is therefore rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. It is subsequently concluded that there is a significant relative influence of compensation on teachers work commitment. Table 4.2.2 also revealed that teachers work commitment can be predicted from compensation by means of the regression equation:

$$\text{Teachers Work Commitment} = (0.461 \times \text{compensation}) + 9.067$$

Hypothesis Three

H03: There is no significant relative influence of performance appraisal on teachers work commitment.

Table 5 Coefficient of the simple linear regression analysis for the influence of performance Appraisal on Work Commitment.

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
1 (constant)	7.757	0.976		7.951	0.000
Performance Appraisal	0.497	0.058	0.586	8.515	0.000

Dependent Variable: Work commitment

Results in Table 4.2. were significant (Beta = .586, t= 8.515, p < .05).

The null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant relative influence of performance appraisal on teachers work commitment is therefore rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis.

It is subsequently concluded that there is a significant relative influence of performance appraisal on teachers work commitment. Table 5 also revealed that teachers work commitment can be predicted from performance appraisal by means of regression equation.

$$\text{Work Commitment} = (0.497 \times \text{Performance Appraisal}) + 7.757$$

4. Discussion of Findings

This study was carried out to examine compensation and performance appraisal as determinants of work commitment among teachers in Ikenne. Consequently, three null hypotheses bothering on the influence of both compensation and performance appraisal on teachers work commitment, were formulated.

The first null hypothesis stated that stated that there is no significant combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on teachers work commitment. It was therefore rejected in favor of an alternative hypothesis and was afterwards concluded that there was significant combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on teachers work commitment. The finding is supported by Kumar (2019), who found that compensation plays an important role in determining an employee's level of work commitment. It also supported by Subekti and Setyadi (2016) in their research on the implication of financial compensation and performance appraisal system to job commitment and satisfaction in Timur, Indonesia which found that performance appraisal and compensation have influence on work commitment.

The second null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relative influence of compensation on teachers work commitment which was again rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis and subsequently concluded that there is a significant relative influence of compensation on teachers work commitment. This study corroborates with the findings of Kumar (2016) who claimed that if teachers are compensated well, they will be encouraged, assured and have positive feelings towards their job and this will result to job satisfaction. This is also shared by Werang, Agung and Agung (2017).

Lastly, the third null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relative influence of performance appraisal on teachers work commitment. This was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. It was subsequently concluded that there is significant relative influence of performance appraisal on teachers work commitment. This finding agreed with what one will ordinarily expect since according to Kyeremeh and Pimpong (2018), employees who perceived that recognition of their performance to the organization is linked to their performance appraisal system, have a higher tendency to be committed to their jobs.

5. Conclusions and recommendation

This study comprehensively evaluated compensation and performance appraisal as determinants of work commitment among teachers in Ikenne Local Government, Ogun state Nigeria. Findings indicate that teachers in this area receive mostly monetary compensation packages. Furthermore, findings indicated a significant combined influence of compensation and performance appraisal on teachers' work commitment, significant relative influence of compensation on teachers work commitment and significant relative influence of performance appraisal on work commitment of teachers, hence the researcher recommended that management of schools should compensate teachers for their hard

work not just by monetary means alone but also by recognition as well as this makes them more committed to their work while result of appraisals should be used objectively in decision making.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

The consent of the respondents was obtained to participant in the study.

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